

LuftBlick Report 2023006

PGN Products Uncertainty Validation

Final Report QA4EO WP2127

Version 1 - May 3, 2023

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1 Contents

<u>1 Contents</u>	<u>2</u>
<u>2 Document Change Record</u>	<u>2</u>
<u>3 Introduction, Summary and Conclusions</u>	<u>2</u>
<u>3.1 Acronyms and Abbreviations</u>	<u>3</u>
<u>4 O3 Common Uncertainty Determination</u>	<u>3</u>
<u>4.1 Inclusion in operational processing chain</u>	<u>5</u>
<u>5 Comparisons to external datasets</u>	<u>6</u>
<u>5.1 Dataset sources</u>	<u>6</u>
<u>5.2 O3 Total columns</u>	<u>6</u>
<u>5.3 O3T</u>	<u>7</u>
<u>6 Uncertainty component comparison for total O3 in Davos</u>	<u>9</u>
<u>6.1 Uncertainty components</u>	<u>9</u>
<u>6.2 First attempt in uncertainty comparison for total O3</u>	<u>10</u>
<u>6.3 Total O3 uncertainty comparison between Pandora & Brewer in Davos</u>	<u>10</u>
<u>7 Future work</u>	<u>11</u>

2 Document Change Record

Issue	Date	Section	Observations
1	30 Apr 2023	All	First version

3 Introduction, Summary and Conclusions

The WP2127 “[PGN Products Uncertainty Validation](#)” of the ESA project “Quality Assurance for Earth Observation” ([QA4EO](#)) phase²¹ had the purpose to answer the following questions:

- 1) What is the uncertainty of PGN trace gas columns for retrievals using a reference spectrum from the literature?
- 2) How do time series of new products like O3 effective temperature compare to other data sets?
- 3) How do retrieved O3 column uncertainties compare to the uncertainties given in measurements from other ground-based data sources?

To tackle 1), two versions of O3 data products for seven, globally distributed datasets have been prepared. One version uses a reference spectrum from literature in the retrieval and one version a measured reference spectrum. For the estimation of the common uncertainty of this literature reference, it is assumed that O3 products based on a measured reference are considered the “truth”. Following this, the difference of O3 products based on the two references contain information about the uncertainty attached to the literature reference. As such, we argue that the variance of this difference as a valid estimate for the common uncertainty from the literature reference. This approach assumes that the mean difference between both datasets (=different references) is driven by differences in the temperature considerations (climatology vs. fitted temperature) in the fitting. The median variance (across all sites) represents the final estimate of the common uncertainty using a literature reference, which yields $0.75 (\pm 0.41)$ mmol/m² or about 1.5 DU (in the slant column).

When a measured reference spectrum is used in the algorithm, O3 effective temperatures can be retrieved from Pandora measurements. To our knowledge, O3 temperature is not offered directly by any other instrumentation than Pandora. However, it can be retrieved when O3 profile and temperature information is given. Since ozonesondes (which fulfill this requirement) are very sparse - temporally and spatially - a comparison to MERRA-2 data (available up to every 3 hours on a global scale) might

¹ Quality Assurance for Earth Observation project [Statement of Work for LuftBlick], SERCO Contract QA4EO/SER/SUB/04, 2022.

be a valid possibility for comparison. Question 2) is therefore approached by comparison to MERRA-2 data sets for selected sites. It is shown that the yearly, seasonal and monthly patterns are basically identical between both datasets, solely finer scale variations (weekly, daily) are visible just by Pandoras, to no surprise.

Comparing mean values of data products alone is not sufficient. Instead, mean values have to be considered together with their uncertainties. Uncertainty validation, however, is a difficult task and was approached here qualitatively by contrasting Pandora and Brewer (V2) total O3 uncertainties to tackle question 3). The reported combined (=total) uncertainty of Brewer V2 total O3 is about 3 times higher as for Pandora and is driven by random (=independent) uncertainty for Brewer and - depending on the season - driven by mixed (=structured, in winter) or systematic (=common, in summer) uncertainty for Pandoras.

3.1 Acronyms and Abbreviations

AMF	Air Mass Factor
DO ₃	Difference O ₃ lit - O ₃ meas total column amount
DO ₃ T	Difference O ₃ lit - O ₃ meas effective temperature
EUBREWNET	European Brewer Spectrophotometer monitoring stations
GAM	Generalized Additive regression Model
GEOS-5	Goddard Earth Observing System Model, Version 5
MERRA-2	Modern-Era Retrospective analysis for Research and Applications
O ₃ T	Effective Ozone temperature
O ₃ lit	Total O ₃ based on literature reference
O ₃ meas	Total O ₃ based on measured reference
O ₃	Ozone
PGN	Pandonia Global Network
QA4EO	Quality Assurance for Earth Observation
TOMS	Total Ozone Mapping Spectrometer

4 O₃ Common Uncertainty Determination

The uncertainty reporting within the processing software (Blick Software Suite) is split into three parts. One of those is the common uncertainty which mainly reflects uncertainties related to the residual gas amount in the reference spectrum or other aspects leading to a systematic bias in the data. Therefore this uncertainty component is also often referred to as the systematic uncertainty. More in [section 6](#) of this report.

Currently there is no common uncertainty for total O₃ given when a literature reference is used. The total O₃ based on literature reference (O₃lit) uses O₃ effective temperature (O₃T) climatology (based on multiyear TOMS O₃ profiles). Total O₃ based on measured reference (O₃meas) fits O₃T.

For the uncertainty estimation the assumption is that the median difference between O₃lit and O₃meas is driven by temperature difference and that the residual differences (more precisely its variance) is a suitable estimation for the common uncertainty.

There are also station specific differences, like a bias in O₃T climatology or an imperfect calibration of O₃ and O₃T, which we assume mitigated considering the number of datasets addressed in this study. A suitable technique, which takes advantage of several datasets and their variance, is the application of a [heteroscedastic linear regression model](#). This model can address varying variance.

The approach is to check the dependence of the total O₃ column difference between O₃lit and O₃meas (dO₃), as a function of the difference in the O₃T of O₃lit and O₃meas (dO₃T):

$$\text{Expectation value} \quad \mu = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * dO_3T$$

$$\text{Standard deviation} \quad \log(\sigma) = \gamma_0 + \gamma_1 * dO_3T$$

Herein, the 1-sigma standard deviation (σ) is mainly driven by the regression coefficient γ_0 , which is

used to get the site-specific common-uncertainty under ideal conditions when climatology and retrieved temperature agree, namely $dO_3T=0$. Note that the estimation is done on a log-scale to ensure positivity. The remaining coefficients describe imperfections in calibration, the so-called offset (β_0), the effect of the effective temperature on the column amount (β_1), and the effect of a different effective temperature on the standard deviation (γ_1). This regression model is applied for each dataset separately, and summarized over all coefficients to obtain a representative common uncertainty.

Figure 1 shows the related differences for certain datasets. The common uncertainty is to be evaluated as the standard deviation of the residuals of individual stations fits. Note, NyAlesund (green line) is an outlier, as the climatology is less applicable for high latitude stations due to enhanced O_3 dynamics, as seen in both the intercept and the slope. The intercept of the best fitting line depends on how off each dataset is to the corresponding climatology.

	β_0	β_1	σ_{VC}	σ_{SC}	AMF
P25	-0.71	0.29	0.43	0.75	1.75
P30	-0.75	0.44	0.41	0.57	1.39
P120	0.2	0.3	0.31	0.43	1.37
P150	1.39	0.39	0.77	1.23	1.59
P152	3.26	0.54	0.63	1.56	2.47
P176	-0.76	0.34	0.54	0.8	1.47
P182	-0.19	0.35	0.42	0.58	1.37

Table 1: Regression coefficients and median AMF for $dO_3T= +/-0.05K$.

Figures 2-4 show the same for individual datasets with the $2\text{-}\sigma$ range under consideration of heteroscedasticity. The $2\text{-}\sigma$ in the legends describes 2-times the exponent of γ_0 .

Table 1 presents the individual regression coefficients (effects), and Table 2 the median values and empirical standard deviation of the individual datasets.

Figure 1: O_3 difference related to O_3T difference for different datasets

Figure 2: Pandora 30, Juelich

Figure 3: Pandora 120, Davos

Figure 4: Pandora 182, Tel-Aviv

Offset [mmol/m ₂]	O ₃ T effect [mmol/K]	Common uncertainty [mmol/m ₂]
-0.19 (± 1.5)	0.35 (± 0.09)	0.43 (± 0.16) Vertical Column 0.75 (± 0.41) Slant Column

Table 2: Median values (empirical standard deviation) among the site specific β_0 , β_1 , σ .

In order to implement a proper common uncertainty, a representative AMF-value needs to be used for converting from vertical column uncertainty to slant column uncertainty. This representative value is given in Table 1 for each dataset, which is the median AMF where the absolute dO3T < 0.05K. By multiplying the obtained σ of the vertical column with this AMF, one obtains the σ for the slant column as reported in Table 1, and the aggregated median value over all instruments as reported in Table 2.

4.1 Inclusion in operational processing chain

The currently operational processing software (version 1.8) is not capable of propagating common uncertainties assigned to retrieval settings using a literature reference spectrum. Its inclusion would change the data and calibration compatibility chain and therefore needs to be moved to the next processor version 1.9. This version is already in preparation and will now be extended with this feature.

5 Comparisons to external datasets

5.1 Dataset sources

In order to validate the output of Pandora, both in terms of O_3 total columns and uncertainties, a comparison with external datasets is performed. For this purpose, we need a combination of external datasets, which are presented below.

MERRA-2 (Modern-Era Retrospective analysis for Research and Applications), is a NASA atmospheric reanalysis, based on the Goddard Earth Observing System Model, Version 5 (**GEOS-5**) data assimilation system. MERRA-2 is the only source that provides diurnal variations of O_3T . However, data from MERRA-2 is not considered to be as accurate as those obtained from measurements.

O_3 sondes are lightweight, balloon-borne instruments that are mated to a conventional meteorological radiosonde. It transmits O_3 related data as the balloon ascents. They are the most accurate source for comparison, but very sparse. Also, they provide only one point per day.

EUBREWNET is a coherent network of European Brewer Spectrophotometer monitoring stations in order to harmonize operations and develop approaches, practices and protocols to achieve consistency in quality control, quality assurance and coordinated operations. Regarding O_3T , Brewers use a fixed O_3T in version 1 (V1) and climatologies in version 2 (V2). In the V1 (or standard EUBREWNET data), no uncertainty estimate is given. However, in the V2 of the Brewer data, and similar to Pandoras, the EUBREWNET O_3 total columns come with uncertainty information and are homogeneously calibrated and processed. Therefore, we used V2, which includes the uncertainty components described in section 6.

5.2 O_3 Total columns

In all figures below, Pandora data are quality and **AMF** filtered. O_3 sondes were extrapolated with

MERRA-2 data (below the burst height the sonde is considered, while above MERRA-2):

Figure 5: Comparison of O_3 total column of Pandora 120 in Davos, MERRA-2, O_3 sondes and Brewer data.

For other stations like Rome and Tsukuba no Brewer data was available, but MERRA-2 and O_3 sondes data was.

Figure 6: Comparison of O_3 total column of Pandora 138 in Rome, MERRA-2 and O_3 sondes data.

Figure 7: Comparison of O_3 total column of Pandora 193 in Tsukuba, MERRA-2 and O_3 sondes data.

5.3 O_3T

Similar to the figures above, Pandora data are quality and AME filtered, while O_3 sondes were extrapolated with MERRA-2 data:

Figure 8: Comparison of O_3 temperature of Pandora 120 in Davos, MERRA-2, O_3 sondes and Brewer data.

Figure 9: Comparison of O_3 temperature of Pandora 138 in Rome, MERRA-2 and O_3 sondes data.

Figure 10: Comparison of O_3 temperature of Pandora 193 in Tsukuba, MERRA-2 and O_3 sondes data.

Figure 11: Comparison of O_3 effective temperature between Pandora 120 and MERRA-2 data in Davos (2021-03-01 until 2021-05-31).

Figure 12: Comparison of O_3 effective temperature between Pandora 138 and MERRA-2 data in Rome (2020-03-01 until 2020-05-31).

Figure 13: Comparison of O_3 effective temperature between Pandora 193 and MERRA-2 data in Tsukuba (2022-03-01 until 2022-05-31).

	Correlation	RMSE	Slope
Davos	0.98	0.63	1.08
Rome	0.84	0.88	0.95
Tsukuba	0.90	0.74	0.73

Table 2: Correlation, rms and slope for the different datasets.

The high level of agreement between Pandora and MERRA-2 effective temperature is very encouraging and shows basically identical yearly patterns. However, MERRA-2 based retrievals do not show the more fine scaled (daily, weekly) variations in the temperature, which are visible in the Pandora retrievals.

Note, the somewhat lower correlation coefficient for Rome comes to no surprise, considering Rome a source of significant surface O_3 and the ozonesonde being launched about 100 km to the East.

6 Uncertainty component comparison for total O_3 in Davos

6.1 Uncertainty components

The uncertainty is split into 3 different components, the random, systematic and mixed uncertainty.

The random or independent uncertainty has a zero correlation length in time. An example is the read noise in a certain pixel or the photon noise propagated into the slant column amount measured at a certain moment. The uncertainty associated with an independent error is called "Independent uncertainty".

The systematic or common uncertainty has a correlation length of infinite. An example is a bias in the radiometric calibration due to a faulty current for the calibration lamp in the laboratory or an error in the assumed slant column in the reference spectrum. This error affects all retrieved slant columns using the same reference spectrum in the same way, hence the error at a certain measurement is fully correlated to the error for measurements taken at any other time. The uncertainty associated with a common error is called "Common uncertainty".

The mixed or structured uncertainty has a correlation length larger than zero, but not infinite. An example is a difference between the effective temperature of a trace gas used in the spectral fitting (assuming that the temperature is not fitted itself) and the true effective temperature of this gas in the atmosphere. This introduces an error in the retrieved slant column, which is highly correlated to measurements taken around the same time, but in general not correlated to measurements taken at times farther away. E.g. if an effective ozone temperature of 225 K is used in the spectral fitting, but

the true effective ozone temperature is 228 K at 10:00 in the morning of 27 October, this causes approximately a -1% error in the retrieved ozone slant column. The next measurement on this day at 10:02 will still suffer nearly exactly the same error, since the true temperature has hardly changed in the 2 minutes. However a few days later, on 3 November, the true temperature has in general changed and might be 225 K, which means the error due a mismatch of the effective temperature is then 0 and not correlated to the error from 27 October at 10:00. The uncertainty associated with a structured error is called "Structured uncertainty".

6.2 First attempt in uncertainty comparison for total O₃

Figure 14 shows the uncertainty components comparison between Pandora and Brewer V2 for Davos. It should be stated that the scale in the two panels is different. The left one (Brewer) ranges from 0.5 to 3.5, while the right one (Pandora), from 0.0 to 1.0.

Figure 14: Comparison of O₃ uncertainty for Brewer V2 and Pandora in Davos.

When comparing the O₃ uncertainties of the Brewer V2 (explanation see [here](#)) and the Pandora in Davos, the magnitudes of the different components are different. For the random uncertainty, the different amount of wavelengths play their part: Since Brewer V2 uses 5 wavelengths whereas Pandora uses 200, Pandora shows much less noise. Also, we can observe a seasonality, for both Pandora and Brewer (lower during winter), which is due to an AMF effect (since we divide with an AMF, and it is higher during winters, the total column is lower during these periods). Brewer is driven from random uncertainty, both in magnitude and patterns (it looks identical to the combined uncertainty). For Pandora, the systematic and the mixed parts drive the combined uncertainty. The random uncertainty is much less pronounced, especially in terms of magnitude.

6.3 Total O₃ uncertainty comparison between Pandora & Brewer in Davos

In [figures 15 and 16](#) we see a comparison between the Pandora total O₃ and the Brewer total O₃ for Davos. Figure 15 includes two scatterplots. The one denoted with green color shows all data within the uncertainty threshold (67% of the data), while the dataset denoted with red shows data outside the uncertainty. Figure 16 shows the diurnal variation of O₃ total columns for Pandora and Brewer during a 2 months period.

Figure 15, Figure 16: Comparison of total O_3 between Pandora and Brewer for Davos.

Overall there is an excellent agreement between the two datasets. We see that both datasets in the left panel can be represented well from the corresponding best fitting lines (slope of 0.99 for the dataset within the uncertainty and 0.95 for the one outside). Also, the diurnal O_3 variations agree between the two instruments, with Brewer being a little higher in magnitude and higher scatter for some days (but with higher uncertainties as well).

7 Future work

As a next step the newly developed version 1.9 uncertainty could be included in the PGN instrument calibration procedures in order to prepare the move from version 1.8 to 1.9 as the official PGN retrieval software.

In general, with the exception of O_3 , there is hardly any external (non PGN) direct sun data available for uncertainty comparison. Therefore, a goal would be to extend the validation of PGN data uncertainties using the results of collocated PGN instruments using a statistical framework with Generalized Additive Regression Models (GAMs), in order to obtain a shared daily effect among instruments. The procedure for this is to evaluate the instrument-specific offset to a baseline amount, which describes common (=systematic) uncertainty (\sim calibration error) for which the offset can be corrected in the next step. If there are no other error sources, the remaining variation around the baseline should be attributed to the independent (=random) uncertainty solely, and it can be quantified in terms of statistical consistency.

Figure 17: Different column amounts for 3 instruments.

Figure 18: The shared daily effect can be extracted.

Figure 19: Correct for the offset in between.

The obtained baseline amount must be randomly distributed within the reported independent uncertainty, and the results in uniformly distributed frequencies within equi-distant probability-bins to full-fill statistical consistency.

1. Correct Uncertainty -> Uniform
2. Low Uncertainty -> U-shape
3. High Uncertainty -> inverse U-shape

Figure 20: Distribution of uncertainty

Anderson, J. L., 1996: A method for producing and evaluating probabilistic forecast from ensemble model integration. *J. Climate*, **9**, 1518–1530
Hamill, T. M., and S. J. Colucci, 1998: Evaluation of Eta RSM ensemble probabilistic precipitation forecasts. *Mon. Wea. Rev.*, **126**, 711–724